

DIPOLE MOMENTS FROM DIELECTRIC CONSTANTS OF LIQUIDS. PART I

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Dielectric constants, refractive indices and densities of a series of several organic substances in the liquid state at different temperatures have been determined. The results are used to calculate the dipole moments of these substances by using Onsager's equation. It has been shown that the moments thus calculated agree within reasonable accuracy with those obtained by other methods.

The determination of dipole moments of molecules involves measurement of dielectric constants in the vapour condition or in solution in a non-polar solvent like benzene. The former method requires intricate technique and can be used only for substances which are easily vaporised without decomposition. The latter method (solution method) is laborious and the results are frequently uncertain due to solvent effects.

Böttcher (*Physica*, 1939, 6, 50; 1938, 5, 635) has shown that the dipole moments of many molecules can be obtained easily from a knowledge of the refractive index, density and dielectric constant in the liquid state by the use of Onsager's equation (i) (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 1486).

$$\frac{[\epsilon - n^2] [2\epsilon + n^2]}{\epsilon [n^2 + 2]^2} = \frac{4\pi}{3} \times N \times \frac{\mu^2}{3KT} \quad \dots \quad (i)$$

where ϵ is the dielectric constant, n is the refractive index of the liquid, N is the number of molecules per c.c. i.e. $6.023 \times 10^{23} \times d/M$ and μ is the dipole moment.

In the present work the dielectric constants, refractive indices and densities of several liquids have been measured and the dipole moments have been calculated using Onsager's equation (i).

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials.—All the substances used in this work were either purchased or prepared by standard methods and carefully purified before use.

Apparatus.—Dielectric constants were measured by the resonance method at 100 meter wave-length. The apparatus used was the same as described by Bhide and Bhide (*J. Univ. Bom.*, 1938, 8, iii, 93) and Ghokhale, Phalnikar and Bhawe (*J. Univ. Bom.*, 1943, 11, v, 56). The experimental condenser was of the same type as described by Bhide and Bhide (*ibid.*, 1939, 9, iii, 220).

Densities were measured by means of a pycnometer and refractive indices were measured with a Bausch and Lomb dipping refractometer. No attempt has been made to find the refractive index at infinite wave-length as was done by Böttcher (*loc. cit.*) because, it has been found that no appreciable error is caused thereby.

The dipole moments of the substances were calculated from the dielectric constants, refractive indices and the densities using Onsager's equation (i).

In the following tables the results are summarised along with the moments obtained by using Onsager's equation (i) and the values of the moments obtained by the solution method are given from the literature. Values obtained by the vapour method have also been included wherever they are known.

In cases where divergences between the two values obtained by the two methods were observed and where the dipole moments of substances were not previously determined, the moments have been determined using very dilute solutions in benzene, having concentration below 0.01 mol-fraction.

The details of the method used for calculation have been already described (Phalnikar, Bhide and Nargund, *ibid.*, 1941, 10, *iii*, 48).

Table I gives the relevant data for the moments determined by the solution method.

TABLE I

Substance.	n	β	P_1^*	P_2	μ
Diethyl azelate	3.1122	0.2270	181.93	63.84	2.41
Diethyl sebacate	3.1803	0.2322	188.18	68.59	2.44
Acetophenone	5.2493	0.2794	216.84	35.55	3.00
Salicylaldehyde	5.7165	0.3479	224.60	27.26	3.13

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

(In the following discussion dipole moments are expressed in Debye units).

Table II gives the dielectric constants, refractive indices, densities and moments calculated by Onsager's equation (5) and by the solution method, for various esters. Column 8, gives the differences between the moments obtained by two methods and the last column gives references to the dipole moments obtained by the solution method.

TABLE II

Compound.	Temp.	Dielectric constant.	Density	Refractive index.	μ (Ons.)	μ (Sol.)	Diff.	Ref.
Methyl acetate	30°	6.606	0.9083	1.3513	1.729			(1)
	35	6.475	0.9038	1.3494	1.749	1.74	0.009	
	40	6.385	0.8998	1.3477	1.754			
Ethyl acetate*	25	6.4	0.8940		1.83	1.84	0.01	(1)
	Butyl acetate	30	4.873	0.8765	1.3827	1.82		(1)
		35	4.801	0.8726	1.3808	1.82	1.85	-0.02
	40	4.734	0.8689	1.3798	1.83			
<i>iso</i> Amyl acetate	30	4.539	0.8500	1.3897	1.75			
	35	4.483	0.8488	1.3871	1.76	1.82	-0.06	(1)
	40	4.414	0.8440	1.3846	1.76			
Ethyl stearate	40	2.858	0.8533	1.4349	1.65			(6)
	45	2.930	0.8498	1.4322	1.65	1.65	0.00	
	50	2.996	0.8422	1.4315	1.65			
Diethyl malonate	25	8.181	1.0488	1.4105	2.59	2.54	0.04	(1)
	30	8.045	1.0425	1.4088	2.55			
Diethyl succinate	30	6.636	1.0265	1.4154	2.37			(1)
	35	6.666	1.0239	1.4136	2.37	{ 2.28 (gas) 2.32 }	0.05	
	40	6.533	1.0190	1.4114	2.39			
Diethyl glutarate	30	6.659	1.0144	1.4199	2.46			
	35	6.523	1.0104	1.4181	2.46	2.41	0.05	(1)
	40	6.392	1.0062	1.4154	2.46			
Diethyl azelate	30	5.193	0.9815	1.4284	2.36			
	35	5.047	0.9774	1.4263	2.36	2.41	-0.06	(2)
	40	4.972	0.9738	1.4241	2.36			
Diethyl sebacate	30	4.995	0.9625	1.4255	2.41			
	35	4.925	0.9585	1.4237	2.42	2.43	-0.02	(2)
	40	4.871	0.9539	1.4219	2.43			
Ethoxy ethanol acetate	30	7.567	0.9743	1.4003	2.32			
	40	7.252	0.9664	1.3959	2.32	2.25	0.07	(3)
	50	6.950	0.9586	1.3918	2.31			
Methoxy ethanol stearate	50	3.887	0.8710	1.4364	2.077	2.02	0.05	(3)
Methyl benzoate	30	6.459	1.0798	1.5074	1.83			
	35	6.352	1.0721	1.5032	1.83	1.83	0.00	(1)
	40	6.251	1.0690	1.4987	1.83			
Ethyl benzoate	30	5.991	1.0367	1.4964	1.87			
	35	5.883	1.0324	1.4960	1.87	1.82	0.05	(1)
	40	5.779	1.0279	1.4955	1.87			
Ethyl cinnamate	35	9.4825	1.1143	1.5520	2.09	2.14	-0.05	(1)
	40	9.4193	1.1101	1.5495	2.11			

* Results taken from Böttcher (*loc. cit.*).

From the above table it will be seen that the dipole moments do not vary appreciably within the temperature range used. This is in accordance with the observation of Böttcher (*loc. cit.*).

The maximum differences between the dipole moments obtained by the two methods have been found to be 0.06 to 0.09 units. Hence the agreement in the values of the moments is extremely good.

The moment of diethyl succinate obtained by the vapour method is 2.28 to 2.39 (156°-256°) and is in better agreement with the value obtained by the use of Onsager's equation (2.37) than the value obtained by the solution method (2.21).

Table III records the results obtained in the case of some ethers, ketones and aldehydes.

TABLE III

Compound.	Temp.	Dielectric constant.	Density.	Refractive index.	μ (Ons.)	μ (Sol.)	Diff.	Ref.
Anisole	30°	4.314	0.9877	1.5150	1.22	1.16	0.06	(4)
	35	4.261	0.9809	1.5118	1.22			
	40	4.209	0.9761	1.5085	1.23			
<i>p</i> -Bromoanisole	30	7.063	1.4773	1.4741	2.11	2.23	-0.12	(1)
	35	6.971	1.4741	1.4706	2.11			
	40	6.898	1.4716	1.4658	2.13			
Phenetole	30	4.130	0.9616	1.4993	1.27	1.28 (gas)	-0.01	(1)
	35	4.030	0.9598	1.4952	1.27			
	40	3.995	0.9583	1.4971	1.27			
Diphenyl ether	30	3.684	1.0610	1.4712	1.13	0.88	0.15	(1)
	35	3.650	1.0551	1.4633	1.15			
	40	3.614	1.0490	1.4591	1.15			
Amyl ether	30	2.636	0.7629	1.3980	1.03	0.97	0.06	(1)
	35	2.602	0.7591	1.3965	1.04			
	40	2.567	0.7543	1.3936	1.05			
Ethylmethyl ketone	30	18.35	0.7965	1.3723	3.2	2.77	0.43	(1)
	35	17.92	0.7930	1.3712	3.2			
	40	17.64	0.7889	1.3696	3.2			
Acetophenone	30	16.86	1.2570	1.5299	3.65	2.97	0.68	(1)
	35	16.67	1.2555	1.5283	3.67			
	40	16.47	1.2501	1.5265	3.67			
Benzophenone	50	12.56	1.0976	1.5484	3.08	3.19	-0.05	(1)
	60	12.23	1.0892	1.5480	3.10			
	65	12.13	1.0851	1.5479	3.08			
Acetone*	10	22.64	0.8020		3.13	2.97 (gas)	0.16	(1)
	20	21.40	0.7910		3.13			
Acetaldehyde*	10	21.80	0.7930		2.74	2.72 (gas)	0.02	(1)

The values for the moments of anisole and diphenyl ether using Onsager's equation have been recently obtained by Jacob, Roberts and Macmillan (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 656). The values obtained in the present work agree with their values.

In the case of ethers the variation is small except in the case of *p*-bromoanisole. The deviation of 0.18 in *p*-bromoanisole is appreciable and cannot be explained.

* Results taken from Böttcher (*loc. cit.*).

Among the ketones there is good agreement only in the case of benzophenone, while in ethylmethyl ketone, acetophenone and acetone the deviations are very high. In the case of acetone the deviation may be attributed to the enolic nature leading to association like in other hydroxy compounds.

Table IV gives the results obtained in the case of different types of compounds such as nitroaniline, nitrochlorobenzenes etc.

TABLE IV

Compound.	Temp.	Dielectric constant.	Density.	Refractive index	μ (Ons.)	μ (Sol.)	Diff.	Ref.
<i>p</i> -Nitroaniline	160°	56.27	1.1786	1.5401	7.09	7.1	-0.01	(1)
	170	55.61	1.1413	1.5229	7.14			
	180	55.06	1.1192	1.5130	7.24			
<i>o</i> -Nitroaniline	90	34.530	1.1991	1.5431	4.97	4.72	0.25	(5)
	100	34.160	1.1682	1.5562	5.00			
	110	33.962	1.1336	1.5232	5.03			
<i>m</i> -Chloronitrobenzene	55	13.95	1.1761	1.4771	3.22			(1)
	60	13.61	1.1293	1.4553	3.32	3.38	-0.06	
	65	13.29	1.0912	1.4416	3.40			

The nitroanilines have comparatively high melting points. The variation of dipole moments with temperature in these cases is of the order of 0.1 unit which may be attributed to experimental errors because at such high temperatures accurate measurements of densities are difficult.

The agreement between the values of moments by the two methods for the compounds listed above is satisfactory.

From the above discussion it will be seen that the dipole moments calculated by the Onsager's equation in the case of esters, aldehydes, ketones, ethers etc. are in agreement with the values obtained by the solution method. This is in agreement with the conclusions of Böttcher (*loc. cit.*) and Jacobs *et al* (*loc. cit.*).

Wilson (*Chem. Rev.*, 1939, 25, 377) has criticised Böttcher's calculations and is of the opinion that this agreement is theoretically surprising and is probably due to fortuitous cancellation of errors. In spite of this remark, the method appears to give correct moments and can be safely relied on and used at least as an empirical equation.

The following is a list of references for dipole moments obtained by solution or gas method taken from literature and referred to in the last column of the tables used in the above discussion.

- (1) Table of Dipole Moments. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1934.
- (2) Present work.
- (3) Gokhale, Phalnikar and Bhawo. *J. Univ. Bom.* 1943, 11, v, 56.
- (4) Roberts, MacMiller and Jacob, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 857.
- (5) Kubo, *Sci. Papers Inst. Phys. & Chem. Research*, Tokyo, 1935, 26, 242.
- (6) From analogy with other aliphatic esters.